

KEY FACTS

What are we aiming for?

- 86+** Clinical repositories with genomics data connected across 15 EU countries
- 15%** Accuracy improvement in specific genomic markers for prognosis and treatment
- 20%** Increase in the adoption of open standards for -omics data per clinical site
- 80%** Time reduction in AI analysis and model training through Supercomputing

INNOVATION

INTEROPERABILITY

TRUST

SCALABILITY

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

OUR TEAM

Visit our [website](http://www.genomed4all.eu) to learn more!
www.genomed4all.eu

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

Transforming the response to Hematological Diseases by seizing the power of Artificial Intelligence

Follow us!

@genomed4all

company/genomed4all

About Hematological Diseases

Most have a genetic background

They represent a growing public health challenge

EU repositories are unconnected

Exploring new models in genomics for precision medicine

GenoMed4All will deploy 'white box' AI models in 3 real-world pilots for common and rare hematological diseases

Diagnosis

Prognosis

Treatment

A quantum leap in advanced precision medicine, pooling genomic/ '-omics' health data through a secure and trustworthy Federated Learning platform

Unleashing the power of Artificial Intelligence

The massive connection of -omics and clinical data repositories across Europe offers:

More accurate Deep Neural Networks regression and classification models

Explicit features extraction using advanced generative models such as Variational Autoencoders and Generative Adversarial Networks

Optimal fusion architectures using heterogeneous data as a combination of feedforward, convolutional and recurrent networks

Myelodysplastic Syndromes

Prevention based on Genomic Screening
Omics-based Classification and Prognosis
Omics-based Clinical Decision Making
Drug Repurposing

Multiple Myeloma

Understand Disease Complexity
Identify Evolution Dynamics
Study Risk Progression
Integrate Radiomics and Radiogenomics

Sickle Cell Disease

Gene mutations linked to inflammation markers
AI allocation to a sickling risk profile
Combined models to predict clinical outcomes
AI-based Radiomics

